

Sustainable HRM, Well-Being and Employee Outcomes in Maritime Sector Employees

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Abstract

The increasing awareness of both the intensive use of natural resources and the physical and mental well-being of society has amplified interest in organizational sustainability. Sustainable Human Resource Management (SHRM) integrates human resource strategies, policies, and practices with long-term sustainability objectives. In this study, SHRM is conceptualized through three key dimensions: decent work (fair wages, safe conditions, equity), workplace democracy (employee voice and participation), and sustainable career climate (opportunities for learning and employability). These dimensions align with the Ability–Motivation–Opportunity (AMO) framework, in which SHRM practices are understood as mechanisms that develop employees' competencies (ability), foster intrinsic motivation (motivation), and enhance participation in decision-making (opportunity).

This study investigates the mediating role of employee well-being in the relationship between SHRM practices, job satisfaction, and turnover intention. A quantitative survey was conducted with 467 employees

in the Turkish maritime sector, a high-pressure industry where sustainable work practices are critical for employee retention. Using structural equation modeling (AMOS-SEM), the findings indicate that SHRM practices significantly enhance well-being and job satisfaction, while reducing turnover intention. Furthermore, well-being was found to mediate the relationship between SHRM and both job satisfaction and turnover intention. These results reinforce the strategic value of SHRM practices in high-demand industries by highlighting their capacity to foster sustainable employee outcomes. The study provides practical implications for managers and HR professionals seeking to integrate socially sustainable practices into organizational systems, particularly in contexts where human capital sustainability is a strategic imperative.

Keywords: Sustainable HRM, Job Satisfaction, Turnover Intention, Well-Being, Maritime Sector.

JEL Codes: D23, M12, I10

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1. Introduction

The increasing pressure on organizations to address not only economic but also environmental and social concerns has prompted a growing emphasis on Sustainable Human Resource Management (SHRM). Unlike conventional HRM, which primarily focuses on performance and efficiency, SHRM integrates long-term sustainability objectives—social justice, environmental responsibility, and economic resilience—into HR strategies, policies, and practices (Eh-nert et al., 2016; Kramar, 2014). In this context, SHRM seeks to balance organizational effectiveness with the protection and development of human and natural resources, thereby contributing to sustainable development goals.

This study adopts a multidimensional conceptualization of SHRM based on the framework proposed by Guerci et al. (2015) and operationalized by Dubois and Dubois (2012), which includes three core dimensions: decent work, workplace democracy, and sustainable career climate. These dimensions address not only the social but also the developmental and ethical aspects of human resource practices. First, decent work includes fair wages, safety, equal opportunities, and work-life balance, reflecting the social protection and dignity of labor (ILO, 2015). Second, workplace democracy emphasizes participative decision-making, employee voice, and organizational justice, fostering a culture of mutual respect and transparency (Wilkinson et al., 2010). Third, the sustainable career climate promotes continuous learning, internal mobility, and long-term employability, ensuring the adaptability of both the employee and the organization (De Prins et al., 2014).

These SHRM dimensions are theoretically aligned with the Ability–Motivation–Opportunity (AMO) framework, which posits that organizational performance and employee outcomes improve when employees have the ability to perform (through skills and knowledge), the motivation to exert effort, and the opportunity to participate (Appelbaum et al., 2000). Specifically, sustainable career climate enhances ability via continuous development; decent work improves motivation through fair and humane treatment; and workplace democracy increases opportunity by encouraging active participation in organizational processes.

Among the key outcomes of SHRM, employee well-being has emerged as a crucial mediating variable in the pathway to desirable workplace outcomes. Well-being encompasses both hedonic dimensions (such as life satisfaction and positive affect) and eudaimonic aspects (such as personal growth and purpose) (Ryan & Deci, 2001). Numerous studies

have shown that SHRM practices improve employee well-being by providing psychological safety, social support, and a sense of meaning at work (Zaugg et al., 2001; Lyubomirsky et al., 2005). In turn, well-being has been found to positively influence job satisfaction, a central construct in HRM that reflects employees' evaluative judgments of their work, and to reduce turnover intention, which represents the likelihood of voluntary departure from the organization (Goetz et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2017).

While the positive impacts of SHRM on well-being, job satisfaction, and retention are increasingly acknowledged in theory, there is a lack of empirical research exploring these relationships in high-demand sectors, where employees face heightened physical and psychological stress. The maritime sector, in particular, is characterized by long working hours, isolation, hazardous environments, and exposure to volatile economic conditions. These factors heighten the relevance of SHRM, especially in emerging economies like Turkey, where maritime operations are both strategically vital and socially challenging (Håvold, 2005; Sanrı & Kamanlı, 2020). Despite this, SHRM has received limited scholarly attention in the context of maritime employment.

To address this gap, the present study investigates the mediating role of employee well-being in the relationship between SHRM practices and two key outcomes: job satisfaction and turnover intention, using data collected from 467 employees in the Turkish maritime sector. The analysis is grounded in the AMO framework and social exchange theory, which together provide a basis for understanding how investments in employee sustainability generate reciprocal employee behaviors and attitudes. The research employs structural equation modeling (AMOS-SEM) to assess both measurement and structural components of the hypothesized model. Instruments used in the study have been validated in previous literature and adapted to the maritime context.

This research contributes to the SHRM literature by extending its theoretical application to a high-stress, under-researched industry and by specifying the mechanisms through which SHRM affects employee outcomes via well-being. From a managerial perspective, the study offers actionable insights for human resource professionals aiming to strengthen retention and satisfaction while advancing organizational sustainability. By linking SHRM with both individual and organizational performance through a nuanced understanding of well-being, this study enhances the evidence base for strategic HRM in contexts where it is most needed.

2. Theoretical Background and Hypothesis Development

2.1. Sustainable Human Resource Management as a Predictor of Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention

Since the 1980s, strategic human resource management (SHRM) has emerged as the dominant paradigm in human resource management (HRM). A pivotal development in this field was the establishment of a direct link between HRM practices and financial performance (Huselid, 1995). Scholars have primarily drawn on the resource-based view (Barney, 2001) and the abilities-motivation-opportunities (AMO) framework (Appelbaum et al., 2000) to explain the HRM-performance nexus. These perspectives emphasize that organizations must create the necessary motivation and opportunities for employees, assuming that human capital is the most valuable and developable resource. The notion that HRM enhances knowledge, skills, and behaviors through structured HR practices, ultimately improving performance, has gained widespread acceptance (Paauwe & Boselie, 2005).

Since the 2010s, SHRM has evolved to incorporate sustainability concerns, shifting its focus beyond financial outcomes to encompass broader individual, organizational, and societal impacts (Kramar, 2014). This transformation has been driven by increased attention to organizational sustainability and corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives. Organizational sustainability is defined as “meeting the needs of a firm’s direct and indirect stakeholders (such as shareholders, employees, clients, pressure groups, communities, etc.), without compromising its ability to meet the needs of future stakeholders” (Dyllick & Hockerts, 2002, p. 131). CSR, a core dimension of sustainability, underscores that organizations bear not only economic and legal responsibilities but also ethical obligations. Unlike short-term initiatives, CSR requires organizations to consider long-term stakeholder needs and align their objectives with broader societal values. As a result, for HRM to meaningfully contribute to sustainability, it must extend its focus beyond short-term financial gains to long-term organizational resilience and positive employee outcomes (Wilkinson et al., 2001).

SHRM is conceptualized as the adoption of HRM strategies and practices that align financial, social, and ecological objectives, ensuring a positive impact both within and beyond the organization while mitigating negative consequences (Ehnert et al., 2016: 90). This perspective shifts the focus from short-term financial performance to long-term value creation for multiple stakeholders. The SHRM framework comprises human capital, HRM strategy, HR policies, and HR practices (Kramar, 2014). While discussions persist regarding the specific practices en-

compassed within SHRM, there is broad agreement that these practices contribute to positive individual, social, and environmental outcomes (Ehnert, 2006). From an operational and managerial standpoint, SHRM practices include policy development, implementation, performance evaluation, employee empowerment, skill development, and autonomy facilitation (Chams & Garcia-Blandon, 2019). Diaz-Carrion et al. (2018) further identify key SHRM practices such as staffing, training, performance evaluation, career management, compensation, work-life balance, diversity promotion, and occupational health and safety.

In line with this evolving conceptualization, the present study adopts the operationalization of SHRM proposed by Guerci et al. (2015), which identifies three key dimensions of SHRM: decent work, workplace democracy, and sustainable career climate. Decent work encompasses fair compensation, occupational safety, equitable treatment, and work-life balance initiatives. Workplace democracy refers to participative decision-making, employee voice, and transparent organizational practices that foster fairness and inclusion. The sustainable career climate dimension includes initiatives that support long-term employability, continuous learning, and professional development. These dimensions are conceptually aligned with the Ability-Motivation-Opportunity (AMO) framework (Appelbaum et al., 2000): sustainable career climate initiatives develop employees’ abilities; decent work practices foster motivation by ensuring respectful, safe, and supportive environments; and workplace democracy expands employees’ opportunities to engage meaningfully in organizational processes. This alignment reinforces the theoretical consistency between SHRM and the AMO model, offering a robust framework for examining how sustainable HR practices influence employee outcomes such as job satisfaction and turnover intention.

Job satisfaction, a core HRM construct, refers to an individual’s overall sense of fulfillment in their job (Locke, 1969). It is influenced by both intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Herzberg et al. (1959) classify intrinsic factors as elements such as responsibility, skill development, and personal achievements, which contribute to self-actualization. Intrinsic job satisfaction is driven by the inherent characteristics of work rather than external rewards (Tietjen & Myers, 1998). Research suggests that intrinsic factors exert a stronger influence on job satisfaction than extrinsic factors (Kalleberg, 1977; Wernimont, 1966). Goetz et al. (2012) found that the ability to apply one’s skills significantly impacts job satisfaction. This relationship is particularly relevant in SHRM, as sustainable HR practices prioritize employee development and fulfillment (Grant, 2008). Job satisfaction, in turn, serves as a key predictor of job performance (Ziegler et al., 2012), work engagement (Garg et al., 2017), and organizational commitment (Ćulibrk et al., 2018).

HRM practices have been consistently shown to positively influence job satisfaction (Ileana Petrescu & Simmons, 2008; Jiang et al., 2012). SHRM further enhances person-organization fit, aligning employee needs and values with those of the organization, which strengthens job satisfaction (Gully et al., 2013). From this perspective, Sypniewska et al. (2023) identify well-being, development, and retention as key SHRM dimensions positively associated with job satisfaction. Similarly, Davidescu et al. (2020) examine employee development and work characteristics as SHRM components, demonstrating their positive impact on job satisfaction. The AMO framework further suggests that a workplace conducive to employee development fosters positive work-related attitudes (Marin-Garcia & Tomas, 2016). Cahyadi et al. (2022) conceptualize SHRM as a combination of collaborative, high-involvement, and commitment-based HRM practices, all of which contribute to job satisfaction.

Despite growing research, consensus on the specific practices encompassed by SHRM remains elusive. Wojtczuk-Turek et al. (2024) examined the SHRM–job satisfaction relationship across 54 countries, highlighting the role of organizational identification and cultural dimensions, such as individualism-collectivism, in shaping this relationship. Given cross-cultural variations, further research is necessary to explore the influence of SHRM on job satisfaction across different organizational and national contexts. Based on the AMO framework, SHRM's long-term, employee-centered approach is expected to enhance job satisfaction. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Sustainable HRM practices are positively related to job satisfaction.

Organizations depend on employees who demonstrate high levels of commitment and dedication to maintain a competitive advantage in the labor market (Joo & Park, 2010). However, increasing labor mobility and the evolving nature of business environments have made employee retention an escalating challenge. As a result, employee turnover has remained a central focus in academic research (Allen & Griffeth, 2000). Turnover intention is shaped by multiple antecedents, including work engagement (Halbesleben et al., 2008), perceptions of organizational justice (Loi et al., 2006), and experiences of burnout (Bartram et al., 2012). Among these, work characteristics play a crucial role, encompassing psychosocial factors such as job demands, workplace bullying, and discrimination (Bakker et al., 2021), alongside structural conditions like working hours and workload (Liu et al., 2016).

HRM practices have been widely recognized as effective mechanisms for creating an empowering work environment and reducing turnover intention by fostering knowledge sharing and organizational sup-

port (Islam et al., 2023). Furthermore, the adoption of socially responsible HRM strategies significantly decreases turnover by strengthening employees' sense of belonging and perceptions of fairness within the organization (Nie et al., 2017). Research also highlights that sustainability-driven HRM practices enhance employee retention by fostering long-term commitment and job embeddedness (Jam & Jamal, 2020). Supporting this perspective, Cachon-Rodríguez et al. (2022) demonstrate that SHRM strengthens employee retention by leveraging social capital as a mediating factor.

SHRM embodies a strategic approach aimed at cultivating long-term employment relationships by fostering a humane and ethical work environment (Peiró et al., 2023). By prioritizing employee well-being, SHRM enhances organizational embeddedness, thereby increasing employees' intention to remain with their employers (Almagharbeh et al., 2023). Additionally, SHRM promotes development opportunities and intrinsic motivation, both of which serve as key drivers of employee retention. Employees who perceive opportunities for growth, skill development, and personal fulfillment within their organizations are more likely to develop long-term career commitments. Based on this framework, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Sustainable HRM practices are negatively related to turnover intention.

2.2. The Mediating Role of Well-Being in the Relationship Between Sustainable HRM, Job Satisfaction, and Turnover Intention

Employee well-being, a central outcome in sustainable HRM frameworks, is widely acknowledged as a multidimensional construct encompassing both subjective and objective components (Ryff, 1989; Diener, 2000). Objective well-being refers to tangible life conditions such as health status, income, and living standards, whereas subjective well-being reflects individuals' cognitive and emotional evaluations of their lives. Subjective well-being is further conceptualized through two distinct perspectives: the hedonic view, which emphasizes life satisfaction and affective pleasure, and the eudaimonic view, which highlights self-realization, meaning, and personal growth (Ryan & Deci, 2001; Deci & Ryan, 2008).

While both dimensions are theoretically valuable, this study focuses on subjective well-being, in alignment with prior SHRM literature (Goetz et al., 2012; Islam et al., 2023), as it captures employees' immediate cognitive and emotional experiences related to their work. This analytical choice is particularly relevant in high-demand sectors such as maritime services, where job-related stressors directly influence affective states and perceived well-being.

SHRM practices are posited to promote well-being through mechanisms such as fair treatment, meaningful work, safe working conditions, and developmental opportunities (Grant, 2008; Zaugg et al., 2001). By addressing both personal and professional needs, SHRM supports employees in maintaining positive psychological functioning, which is known to foster job satisfaction and reduce turnover intention (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005; Wu et al., 2017). Moreover, emerging research highlights the mediating role of well-being in the relationship between HR practices and employee attitudes (Zhang et al., 2019), suggesting that well-being may function as a key psychological mechanism through which SHRM exerts its effect. Based on this theoretical foundation, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Sustainable HRM practices are positively related to well-being.

Job satisfaction is shaped not only by employees' perceptions of their work and working conditions but also by the alignment of these perceptions with their expectations and value systems (Schneider & Snyder, 1975). At the organizational level, factors such as leadership style (Altaş et al., 2024; Braun et al., 2013), compensation, work environment, and organizational climate have been shown to significantly influence job satisfaction (Herzberg et al., 1959; Gündüz Çekmecelioğlu, 2005). Research further suggests that fair compensation, a supportive work environment, and career development opportunities enhance job satisfaction, which in turn contributes to greater overall life satisfaction (Kosec et al., 2022; Wright et al., 2007).

Individuals with high levels of well-being tend to experience more positive emotions, enabling them to manage workplace challenges more effectively, ultimately leading to higher job satisfaction and motivation (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005). Recent findings indicate that well-being is intertwined with family satisfaction, extrinsic job satisfaction (related to job security and salary), and intrinsic job satisfaction (associated with competence and self-determination) (Jarosova et al., 2017). Similarly, Pradenas et al. (2021) demonstrate that both extrinsic factors (e.g., financial stability) and intrinsic factors (e.g., recognition, autonomy) jointly shape subjective well-being. The unique challenges of the maritime profession—such as social exclusion, isolation, and demanding work environments—further underscore the importance of job satisfaction in shaping well-being (McVeigh et al., 2017). Employees in this sector frequently experience high levels of psychological distress and depression (McVeigh et al., 2019), making job satisfaction—rooted in competence, autonomy, and recognition—a crucial factor in enhancing overall well-being. Based on this theoretical foundation, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H4: Well-being is positively related to job satisfaction.

Turnover intention refers to an employee's inclination to voluntarily leave their current position in the foreseeable future (Podsakoff et al., 2007) and is recognized as one of the strongest predictors of actual turnover (Lazzari et al., 2022). Workplace stressors are widely acknowledged as key contributors to turnover intention, as they negatively impact employees' well-being and job satisfaction. Wright and Cropanzano (2004) argue that positive emotions foster favorable job attitudes, which, in turn, strengthen organizational commitment and reduce turnover intention. Conversely, workplace instability, excessive demands, and a tense organizational climate erode employees' sense of attachment, reinforcing their likelihood of leaving the organization.

The maritime industry, characterized by unpredictable working conditions, high occupational risks, and long working hours, presents unique challenges that contribute to high turnover intention (Håvold, 2005). Employees in this sector frequently experience excessive workloads, extended work shifts, and high-pressure environments, all of which can elevate stress and turnover intention. However, subjective well-being may serve as a psychological buffer, mitigating the negative effects of these challenging conditions (Wu et al., 2017). Employees with higher levels of well-being are more resilient to workplace stressors and more likely to remain engaged and committed to their organizations despite challenging work environments. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H5: Well-being is negatively related to turnover intention.

A meta-analysis conducted by Judge and Kammerer-Mueller (2011) established that the core components of subjective well-being serve as key antecedents of job satisfaction. Similarly, a longitudinal study by Bowling et al. (2010) identified a reciprocal relationship between job satisfaction and subjective well-being, with subjective well-being exerting a stronger influence on job satisfaction than vice versa. These findings underscore the critical role of well-being in shaping employees' perceptions of their work experiences. Research further highlights the significance of organizational policies that support work-life balance (Nunes & Rodrigues, 2024) and initiatives aimed at enhancing employee well-being (Dagenais-Desmarais & Savoie, 2012). Sustainable HRM (SHRM) integrates these elements by fostering self-efficacy, career commitment, and subjective well-being through programs that facilitate career development and long-term employability (Mariappanadar, 2022). Moreover, SHRM promotes a positive work environment by implementing inclusive practices that engage employees in decision-making processes, ensure fairness and job security, and foster positive emotional states (Islam et al., 2023).

While existing research suggests that well-being plays a critical role in the relationship between HRM

and employee performance, further empirical investigation is needed to fully elucidate this connection (Peccei & Van De Voorde, 2019). In this context, well-being is posited as a key mediating factor between HRM practices and employee outcomes. By promoting long-term employment stability, career and performance development, and work-life balance, SHRM is expected to enhance overall well-being. A work environment that fosters fulfillment and well-being is, in turn, likely to contribute to greater job satisfaction. Based on this theoretical framework, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H6: The relationship between SHRM and job satisfaction is mediated by well-being.

In an organization, both the substance of HR policies and employees' perceptions of them play a critical role in shaping work-related outcomes (Wright & Nishii, 2013). When SHRM is implemented as a long-term approach that prioritizes employees' well-being and professional development, it promotes trust, strengthens organizational commitment, and ultimately reduces turnover intention. Employee retention is influenced by multiple factors, including perceived organizational support, career development opportunities, favorable working conditions, competitive compensation, and comprehensive benefits. These elements collectively contribute to employee commitment and willingness to remain with the organization (James & Azungah, 2020; Choi

et al., 2013; Lam et al., 2013).

By fostering a positive work environment, SHRM enhances employee well-being, which in turn reduces turnover intention. Research has demonstrated that SHRM practices lead to significant improvements in employee attitudes and behaviors. For instance, Lu et al. (2023) found that SHRM enhances employee resilience, work engagement, and overall performance. Similarly, Qamar et al. (2023) reported that SHRM contributes to employee well-being while concurrently lowering turnover intention. Although SHRM remains an evolving field encompassing diverse practices, there is broad consensus on its beneficial effects on employee outcomes (Diaz-Carrion et al., 2018).

These positive outcomes are realized through the development of a supportive and empowering work environment that prioritizes work-life balance and fosters long-term employment relationships. Given that SHRM is designed to nurture and sustain employee relationships, it is expected to significantly decrease turnover intentions. By promoting well-being, SHRM creates an organizational climate in which employees feel valued and engaged, reducing their likelihood of leaving. Based on this theoretical framework, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H7: The relationship between SHRM and turnover intention is mediated by well-being.

Figure 1. Research Model
Source: Figure by the Authors

3. Methodology

3.1. Participants

The study sample consisted of 467 professionals employed in Turkey's maritime sector. Participants were recruited using convenience sampling via an online platform. Prior to participating, respondents gave informed consent by filling out an online form that outlined the study's aims, voluntary participation requirements, and data confidentiality guarantees. Furthermore, ethical permission for the study had been obtained from the authors' associated institution. Despite the utilization of convenience

sampling, the demographic and professional composition of the sample corresponds to the general employee structure of the Turkish maritime sector, hence guaranteeing sufficient representation for this study's objectives. Data were gathered via an online survey platform, enabling participants to reply at their convenience, hence enhancing accessibility across various roles and locations within this sector. Of the participants, 13.5 % (n = 63) were women, while 86.5% (n = 404) were men. The educational distribution of the sample included 24.2% (n = 113) high school graduates, 22.9% (n = 107) associate degree holders, 47.3% (n = 221) bachelor's degree

holders, and 5.6% (n = 26) postgraduates. Regarding professional roles, 73.7% (n = 344) were employees, whereas 26.3% (n = 123) held managerial positions at various levels. The distribution by generations is as follows: 1.5% (n = 7) were born in 1965 or earlier, 16.1% (n = 75) between 1966 and 1979, 54.6% (n = 255) between 1980 and 1999, and 27.8% (n = 130) in 2000 or later.

3.2. Measurement Tools

Sustainable HRM. Employees' perceptions of SHRM were assessed using the 11-item Sustainable HRM Scale developed by De Prins et al. (2020). Each item was rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (completely disagree) to 5 (completely agree). A sample item includes: "Jobs are a reflection of what employees are good at and like to do in our organization." Although SHRM is often conceptualized as a multidimensional construct—encompassing dimensions such as decent work, workplace democracy, and sustainable career climate (Guerci et al., 2015)—in this study, it was operationalized as a unidimensional composite variable. This decision was based on both theoretical and methodological grounds. Conceptually, the dimensions of SHRM are interdependent and collectively represent a unified strategic orientation toward sustainability. Empirically, exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses supported a unidimensional structure with strong internal consistency. Moreover, given the study's focus on examining SHRM's overall influence on employee outcomes, a composite measurement provided a parsimonious and theoretically coherent representation of sustainable HR practices.

Well-Being. Subjective well-being was measured using the 8-item scale developed by Diener et al. (2010). Participants rated their responses on a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 indicated "completely disagree" and 5 indicated "completely agree." Higher scores reflected greater levels of subjective well-being. A sample item is: "I lead a purposeful and meaningful life."

Job Satisfaction. Job Satisfaction was measured using a 15-item, two-dimensional scale developed by Warr et al. (1979), comprising seven items assessing intrinsic job satisfaction and eight items assessing extrinsic job satisfaction. Responses were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Completely Disagree, 5 = Completely Agree). Sample items include "I am satisfied with the freedom to choose my own method of working" (intrinsic job satisfaction) and "I am satisfied with my chance of promotion" (extrinsic job satisfaction).

Turnover Intention. Turnover intention was measured using the 8-item scale developed by Bothma and Roodt (2013). Responses were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale, with higher scores indicating stronger turnover intention. A sample item is: "I often consider leaving my job."

4. Findings

4.1. Measurement Model

First, the normality of the data distribution was assessed by examining skewness and kurtosis values. The skewness values ranged from -0.586 to 0.244, while the kurtosis values ranged from -0.515 to 0.986, indicating that the data distribution approximates normality. Following this, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted using the AMOS software to assess the measurement model. Due to factor loadings exceeding 0.50, two items from the SHRM scale, two from the well-being scale, four from the job satisfaction scale, and two from the turnover intention scale were excluded from the analyses. Subsequent analyses confirmed the validity of the scales. Table 1 presents the CFA results, providing evidence for the validity of the constructs. The model fit was evaluated using multiple fit indices, including Chi-square (χ^2), degrees of freedom (df), χ^2/df ratio, p-value, Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), and Comparative Fit Index (CFI).

Table 1. Confirmatory Factor Analysis Results

Variables	Effect	S.E.	C.R.	p	Standardized Regression Weights	AVE	CR	Cronbach's Alpha
Sustainable HRM								
SHRM1	1.000	-	-	-	.613			
SHRM2	1.195	.086	13.929	***	.633			
SHRM3	1.461	.110	13.300	***	.759			
SHRM4	1.508	.113	13.364	***	.764	.495	.897	.899
SHRM7	1.042	.095	11.006	***	.591			
SHRM8	1.542	.111	13.931	***	.810			

SHRM9	1.284	.104	12.395	***	.688			
SHRM10	1.398	.106	13.241	***	.753			
SHRM11	1.243	.101	12.351	***	.685			
Wellbeing								
WB2	1.000	-	-	-	.691			
WB5	.941	.072	13.140	***	.680			
WB6	.983	.073	13.427	***	.696	.491	.852	.85
WB7	1.274	.092	13.803	***	.718			
WB8	.900	.069	13.076	***	.676			
WB1	1.168	.082	14.166	***	.740			
Job Satisfaction								
Intrinsic Job Satisfaction								
JSI1	1.000	-	-	-	.802			
JSI2	.994	.057	17.569	***	.751			
JSI3	1.009	.065	15.626	***	.683			
JSI5	.952	.053	17.835	***	.759			
JSI6	.859	.052	16.434	***	.713			
JSI7	.847	.051	16.455	***	.712	.644	.782	.877
Extrinsic Job Satisfaction								
JSE2	1.000	-	-	-	.677			
JSE4	1.071	.086	12.393	***	.684			
JSE5	1.011	.086	11.721	***	.639			
JSE7	1.073	.097	11.112	***	.601			
JSE8	1.038	.092	11.252	***	.610			
Turnover Intention								
TT2	1.000	-	-	-	.624			
TT3	1.004	.067	14.978	***	.667			
TT4	1.326	.093	14.333	***	.859	.545	.877	.884
TT5	1.341	.101	13.230	***	.761			
TT6	1.286	.104	12.340	***	.695			
TT7	1.368	.100	13.714	***	.800			

Note. N=467. Items not included in the table were excluded due to factor loadings below 0.5. Model Fit Index: N= 467. $\chi^2 = 1060.828$; df = 451; $\chi^2/df = 2.352$; p = .000; RMSEA = .05; SRMR = .06; CFI = .93.

Source: Table by the Authors.

The four-factor model, consisting of SHRM, well-being, turnover intention, and job satisfaction—the latter modeled and tested as a second-order construct with intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction as its first-order dimensions—demonstrates an accep-

table model fit. The RMSEA value (0.05) and SRMR value (0.06) fall within established acceptable limits, while the CFI value of 0.93 further supports a strong model fit.

Additionally, Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) were calculated as key indicators of construct validity and reliability. Table 1 presents the results of the validity and reliability analysis for SHRM, job satisfaction, well-being, and turnover intention. CR evaluates the internal consistency of the constructs, with values above 0.70 generally considered acceptable (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). As shown in Table 1, the CR values for all constructs exceed this threshold, indicating strong internal consistency.

AVE assesses the proportion of variance explained by a construct's indicators, with a commonly accepted threshold of 0.50, suggesting that at least 50% of the variance is attributed to the latent construct (Hair et al., 2013). The results in Table 1 indicate that the AVE values for the study constructs either meet

or are very close to this threshold. Overall, these findings confirm that the measurement model exhibits a satisfactory level of validity and reliability.

4.2. Structural Model

To test the hypothesized relationships among sustainable HRM, well-being, job satisfaction, and turnover intention, structural equation modeling (SEM) was conducted using AMOS 24.0. The model demonstrated an acceptable overall fit: $\chi^2 = 1061.360$, $df = 452$, $\chi^2/df = 2.348$, CFI = 0.93, RMSEA = 0.05, and SRMR = 0.06. All indices fall within commonly accepted thresholds ($\chi^2/df < 3$; CFI > 0.90; RMSEA < 0.08; SRMR < 0.08), indicating a good fit between the model and the observed data (Hu & Bentler, 1999).

Table 2. Path Results

Path	DE	95% CI	IE	95% CI	TE	95% CI
Sustainable HRM --> Wellbeing	0.499**	[0.374;0.658]			0.499**	[0.374;0.658]
Sustainable HRM --> Job Satisfaction	0.520 **	[0.415;0.665]			0.663**	[0.513;0.843]
Sustainable HRM --> Turnover Intention	-0.798**	[-1.005;-0.625]			-0.907**	[-1.129;-0.706]
Wellbeing --> Job Satisfaction	0.286**	[0.175;0.444]			0.286**	[0.175;0.444]
Wellbeing --> Turnover Intention	-0.217**	[-0.398;-0.054]			-0.217**	[-0.398;-0.054]
Sustainable HRM --> Wellbeing --> Job Satisfaction			0.143**	[0.081;0.232]		
Sustainable HRM --> Wellbeing --> Turnover Intention			-0.108**	[-0.217;-0.030]		

Note. DE = Direct effect; IE = Indirect effect; TE: Total effect; CI = confidence interval, ** $p < 0.01$, $\chi^2 = 1061.360$, $df = 452$, $\chi^2/df = 2.348$, CFI = 0.93, SRMR = .06, RMSEA = .05, $p = .000$

Source: Table by the authors

Table 2 displays the standardized path coefficients, 95% bias-corrected confidence intervals (CIs), and significance levels for both direct and indirect effects, estimated using 5,000 bootstrap resamples.

- **Direct effects:** Sustainable HRM had significant positive effects on well-being ($\beta = 0.499$, $p < .01$, 95% CI [0.374, 0.658]) and job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.520$, $p < .01$, 95% CI [0.415, 0.665]), and a significant negative effect on turnover intention ($\beta = -0.798$, $p < .01$, 95% CI [-1.005, -0.625]). Well-being also positively predicted job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.286$, $p < .01$, 95% CI [0.175, 0.444]) and negatively predicted turnover intention ($\beta = -0.217$, $p < .01$, 95% CI [-0.398, -0.054]).
- **Indirect effects:** SHRM had significant indirect effects on job satisfaction through well-being ($\beta = 0.143$, $p < .01$, 95% CI [0.081, 0.232]) and

on turnover intention through well-being ($\beta = -0.108$, $p < .01$, 95% CI [-0.217, -0.030]). These findings confirm that well-being mediates the effects of SHRM on both outcomes.

- **Total effects:** The total effects of SHRM on job satisfaction (TE = 0.663, 95% CI [0.513, 0.843]) and on turnover intention (TE = -0.907, 95% CI [-1.129, -0.706]) remained statistically significant, affirming the cumulative influence of both direct and mediated pathways.

These results fully support Hypotheses H1 through H7 and highlight the central role of well-being as a psychological mechanism in the SHRM-outcomes link (See Figure 2). The use of bootstrapped confidence intervals enhances the robustness of the mediation findings by reducing dependency on normality assumptions.

Figure 2. Resulted Model
Source: Figure by the Authors

5. Discussion

This study examines the employee-level outcomes of SHRM, focusing on its impact on job satisfaction and turnover intentions, with a particular emphasis on the mediating role of well-being. The findings provide empirical support for the strategic importance of HRM practices in fostering a supportive work environment and enhancing employee well-being, ultimately contributing to higher job satisfaction and workforce retention.

First, the results confirm that SHRM promotes a work environment where employees experience greater job satisfaction while reducing their turnover intention. When organizations integrate SHRM strategies, employees perceive their workplace as more supportive, fair, and growth-oriented, which enhances their overall satisfaction (Hauff et al., 2018; Diaz Carrion et al., 2018). By prioritizing long-term value over short-term efficiency, sustainable HRM policies instill a sense of stability and purpose, strengthening employees' connection to their roles (Grant, 2008; Cachon-Rodríguez et al., 2022). Moreover, these strategies significantly reduce turnover intention, as employees working in organizations that emphasize fairness, consistency, and long-term employee investment are less likely to seek alternative employment (Kramar, 2014; Islam et al., 2023). These results reinforce the idea that sustainable HRM is not solely concerned with policies; rather, it involves the development of a work environment that prioritizes consistency and satisfaction (Ziegler et al., 2012). This finding aligns with recent international evidence from the maritime sector, where Yuen et al. (2018) found that seafarers' job satisfaction is highly dependent on support from management, fair scheduling, and decent working conditions—all core concerns of SHRM. Similarly, a 2024 global seafarer survey showed that well-being and happiness onboard are significant predictors of retention, directly affected

by organizational treatment and perceived fairness (Hayes-Mejia & Stafström, 2024).

Second, the findings demonstrate that SHRM positively influences well-being, revealing that SHRM is more than an administrative function; it is a foundational element of a healthy work environment. Employees in organizations with a structured, long-term HR vision report higher well-being, as they experience a workplace that prioritizes psychological safety, stability, and a sense of belonging (Cooper et al., 2019; Peiró et al., 2023). This is consistent with research that indicates that well-being is not simply a consequence of effective HRM, but rather a direct result of the structure of organizations' people management strategies (Wright & Cropanzano, 2004; Kowalski & Loretto, 2017). This finding resonates with studies from other high-pressure sectors such as logistics and healthcare, where sustainable HRM practices have been found to buffer employees from stress and enhance their psychological well-being (Čižiūnienė et al., 2025; Armeanu et al., 2023). In particular, in crisis-prone logistics contexts, SHRM has been shown to reduce attrition and boost resilience through flexible policies and well-being initiatives.

Third, the results confirm that well-being is a key determinant of both job satisfaction and turnover intention. Employees with higher well-being derive greater satisfaction from their roles, as they perceive alignment between their professional aspirations and organizational practices (Danna & Griffin, 1999; Diener et al., 2010). Similarly, those with stronger well-being are less likely to leave, as they feel more embedded in an environment that meets both their professional and personal expectations (Wright & Cropanzano, 2004; Wu et al., 2017). These findings suggest that organizations seeking to enhance job satisfaction and reduce turnover must first address employee well-being as a strategic priority (Podsakoff et al., 2007; Lazzari et al., 2022). From a global

perspective, similar conclusions were drawn by Simha Vihari et al. (2024), who demonstrated that sustainable HRM boosts employees' well-being and empowerment through ethical and supportive organizational climates. This cross-national alignment supports the generalizability of the SHRM–well-being–performance model beyond a single sector or country.

Finally, the results establish that well-being mediates the relationship between SHRM, job satisfaction, and turnover intention, reinforcing its role as the mediator between HRM practices and employee outcomes. Employees in organizations that treat HRM as a sustainable, long-term investment rather than a short-term operational necessity experience higher well-being, which in turn strengthens job satisfaction and decreases turnover (Ryan & Deci, 2001; Kowalski & Loretto, 2017). These findings underscore that sustainable HRM is not merely an ethical responsibility but a strategic necessity, essential for fostering long-term organizational stability and employee well-being (Dagenais-Desmarais & Savoie, 2012; Liu et al., 2019). Research in Turkey's maritime sector has identified significant relationships among HRM, job satisfaction, and turnover intention. Yorulmaz (2024) discovered that alienation from work in marina and yacht firms elevates turnover intention, particularly due to low job satisfaction and limited organizational support, which intensify this tendency. Arıcan's (2025) research highlights the significance of improvements in factors such as compensation and working conditions to improve job satisfaction and diminish turnover intention. This study's results, although corroborating previous findings, offer a fresh approach by demonstrating that SHRM affects job satisfaction and turnover intention through a mediating effect of subjective well-being. Importantly, by framing these effects within a formal SEM structure and drawing on a multi-dimensional understanding of well-being, this study aligns with and expands on international models proposed in sectors like healthcare (Armeanu et al., 2023), logistics (Čižiūnienė et al., 2025), and maritime (Yuen et al., 2018; Hayes-Mejia & Stafström, 2024).

The results of this study offer important perspectives for HRM policies and sustainability plans. The findings indicate that SHRM practices improve subjective well-being, job satisfaction, and retention, particularly in high-stress sectors, hence underlining the necessity of incorporating SHRM into organizational policy. Human resources professionals and organizational leaders are encouraged to use sustainable and employee-centric strategies to enhance workforce retention and foster long-term success and competitive advantage. These observations highlight the importance of synchronizing HRM programs with broader sustainability objectives, especially in sectors characterized by demanding working conditions and operational difficulties.

5.1. Theoretical Contributions

This study advances the AMO model (Appelbaum et al., 2000) by demonstrating the mediating role of well-being in the relationship between SHRM, job satisfaction, and turnover intention. The AMO framework suggests that organizational performance is maximized when HRM practices enhance employees' abilities, motivate them effectively, and provide opportunities for meaningful engagement (Guest, 2017; Marin-Garcia & Tomas, 2016). First, this study extends AMO by positioning well-being as a central mechanism rather than a passive outcome of HRM interventions. Usually, the AMO model regards well-being as a subsequent result of HRM activities, whereas our findings indicate that well-being serves as an active mediator of the influence of SHRM on job attitudes (Van De Voorde et al., 2012; Wright & Cropanzano, 2004). Second, this study strengthens the motivation component of AMO by demonstrating that SHRM enhances motivation indirectly through well-being. Employees with higher well-being are more likely to be engaged, and satisfied, and less inclined to leave their organizations (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005; Wright & Nishii, 2013). The findings suggest that SHRM enhances motivational mechanisms by fostering psychologically safe, empowering, and fulfilling workplaces (Peiró et al., 2023).

5.2. Practical Implications

The findings underscore the importance of integrating well-being initiatives into HRM strategies to enhance job satisfaction and employee retention (Nunes & Rodrigues, 2024). Organizations operating in high-risk industries, such as the maritime sector, where employees experience long working hours, psychological strain, and hazardous conditions (McVeigh et al., 2017), can particularly benefit from SHRM practices. By implementing work-life balance policies, job security measures, and participative decision-making mechanisms, organizations can cultivate a work environment that supports employees' psychological and physical well-being while strengthening organizational commitment.

Moreover, given the negative association between SHRM and turnover intention, organizations should focus on retention-driven HRM strategies such as career development programs, leadership support initiatives, and well-being-focused workplace interventions. Addressing employees' mental and physical health needs can help reduce turnover risks and promote long-term retention. Furthermore, HR policies should be adapted to address sector-specific challenges, particularly in industries with demanding work conditions. SHRM should include fatigue management programs, social support mechanisms, and stress reduction initiatives, ensuring employees feel valued and supported both professionally and personally (McVeigh et al., 2019; Zaderei, 2020).

5.3. Limitations and Future Research

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations. The reliance on cross-sectional data limits causal inference, highlighting the need for longitudinal studies to track the long-term effects of SHRM on employee outcomes (Podsakoff et al., 2003). Additionally, the sample is limited to maritime industry employees in Turkey, which, while relevant given the sector's challenges, restricts generalizability to other industries and cultural contexts. Future research should explore cross-sector and cross-cultural comparisons to assess whether these findings hold across different workplace settings (Hofstede, 1980). Furthermore, the study is based on self-reported data, which introduces a potential risk of common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003). Future research should incorporate multi-source data collection, including supervisor assessments, HR policy audits, and objective turnover data, to enhance measurement validity. While well-being is identified as a mediating factor, additional variables such as leadership style, job autonomy, and organizational support may also shape the SHRM–job satisfaction and SHRM–turnover intention relationships (Cooper et al., 2019). Future research could examine moderated mediation models to identify the conditions under which SHRM exerts its strongest effects. Lastly, while this study focuses on employee-level outcomes, future research should explore the broader organizational implications of SHRM, including its effects on financial performance, innovation capacity, and long-term corporate sustainability (Ehnert et al., 2016; Chams & Garcia-Blandon, 2019).

5.4. Conclusion

This study emphasizes the significance of SHRM in promoting well-being, increasing job satisfaction, and increasing employee retention, especially in high-demand and high-stress work contexts such as the maritime sector. This research positions subjective well-being as a critical mediating factor, enhancing the AMO paradigm and demonstrating how SHRM practices may lead to positive employee outcomes that promote long-term organizational sustainability. The empirical findings provide significant, evidence-based insights for HR practitioners and managers in organizations aiming to formulate and execute HR strategies that prioritize employee well-being and satisfaction along with performance goals. These insights are particularly essential for industries with distinct psychological and operational difficulties. This study emphasizes the need to incorporate sustainability concepts into HRM to develop adaptable and engaged employees that can maintain a competitive advantage. Future research should further explore the dynamic and developing connection of sustainability, human resource man-

agement, and employee experience across numerous sectors. Such research would enhance comprehension of how SHRM supports organizational resilience and human capital development, ensuring employees remain central to sustainable business success.

6. Data Availability

The data is available upon any reasonable request.

7. Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the researchers' institution.

8. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

9. Financial Support

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